

Spectrophotometric Determination of Physical Parameters of a Weak Base

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Hydroxamic acids are the acyl derivatives of hydroxylamine. *N*-Arylhydroxamic acids are versatile metal extractants of general formula $R_1NOH.R_2CO$. Besides their applications in different branches of chemistry like analytical¹, nuclear² and bioorganic fields³, their physicochemical properties have received little attention. Solvent extraction is largely concerned with the equilibrium distribution of a solute species between aqueous solution and an immiscible solvent, and the application of a variety of physicochemical techniques has produced a good understanding of the overall principles that govern such extraction equilibria. The present paper investigates some physical constants of analytical importance of *N*-*p*-chlorophenyl-*p*-methylbenzohydroxamic acid.

Such investigations are essential and beneficial in solvent extraction studies, gravimetric estimations and preparative chemistry of such metal extractants.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 represents the data for the partition of the weak base between aqueous phase and immiscible organic solvent and also for solubility and solubility parameter in various organic solvents. As no significant variation in K_D values with total reagent concentration is involved, these values

can be regarded as distribution constants for the monomeric form of the weak base. The ionisation constant of this reagent in water is small, so the concentration of its anionic species in aqueous phase is negligible. K_D values give information about the suitability for extraction work and also for the determination of solubility parameters. The pattern of solubility depends on the structure of the group which is attached to the hydroxamic acid.

According to Hildebrand's theory⁴ of regular solution a quantity δ , called the solubility parameter, is defined as

$$\delta = (\Delta E^V/V)^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta E^V/V$ is the energy of vaporisation per unit volume. The solubility increases with increasing similarity of the solubility parameter values, since the heat of mixing of solute and solvent depends on the difference of their δ values. In the present context, the solubility parameters of this reagent in various organic solvents are calculated following equation (2),

$$\ln \frac{\phi_{1,org}}{\phi_{2,aq}} = \frac{V_1}{RT} [(\delta_o - \delta_{aq})^2 - (\delta_c - \delta_{org})^2] + V_1 \left[\frac{1}{V_{org}} - \frac{1}{V_{aq}} \right] \quad (2)$$

where δ_c is the solubility parameter of solute, ϕ_1 the volume fraction of the solute, ϕ_2 the volume fraction of the solvent in the solution, V_1 the molar volume of the solute, δ_{aq} the solubility

parameter of the aqueous phase, δ_{org} the solubility parameter of the organic phase, V_{org} the volume of the organic solvent, and V_{aq} the volume of the aqueous phase for all organic solvents.

At low concentration of solute,

$$\phi_{\text{aq}} = \phi_{\text{org}} = 1$$

and for the low concentration of solute used in the present investigation, it can be assumed that

$$\frac{x_{1,\text{org}}}{x_{2,\text{aq}}} = \frac{\phi_{1,\text{org}}}{\phi_{2,\text{aq}}} = K_D$$

where x is the mole fraction of the solute and K_D the experimental distribution constant. K_D can thus be related directly to the right-hand-side terms of equation (2).

TABLE 1—SOLUBILITY, PARTITION DATA AND SOLUBILITY PARAMETERS OF *N-p*-CHLOROPHENYL-*p*-METHYLBENZOHYDROXAMIC ACID

Solvent	Solubility g L ⁻¹	K_D	δ_c cal ^{1/2} ml ^{-1/2}
Water	0.01	—	—
Benzene	12.9	401	14.9
Chlorobenzene	9.1	315	14.9
<i>o</i> -Dichlorobenzene	6.2	285	15.1
Toluene	5.5	196	14.7
<i>n</i> -Hexane	0.2	24	14.2
Cyclohexane	0.4	33	14.5
Carbontetrachloride	2.8	152	14.6

For the calculation of molar volume (V_1) the density was determined, which is 1.06 g ml⁻¹. Solubility parameters for water and solvents were considered from literature⁵.

The data on solubility parameters of this weak base showed that the calculated values of δ_c for the solvents investigated are reasonably constant, except for *n*-hexane, which indicates that the properties of *N-p*-chlorophenyl-*p*-methylbenzohydroxamic acid solutions in these solvents are at least similar to those postulated for regular solutions. The δ_c values prove fruitful in choosing proper solvent for extraction and also in extending the range of the extraction method.

Experimental

N-p-Chlorophenyl-*p*-methylbenzohydroxamic acid was prepared by the procedure reported earlier⁶. Chloroform was shaken five to six times with equal volume of water to remove alcohol impurity. It was then distilled and stored in amber bottles in a cool place. A saturated solution of analytical grade ammonium metavanadate was prepared in distilled water. Extraction work was done adequately with HCl (C.P. grade) because any iron present in it did not interfere with the extraction process. All other organic solvents used were of analytical grade.

A Spekol EK-1 (Carl-Zeiss, Jena) instrument was used for the measurement of absorbance at fixed wavelength, using 10 mm matched cells.

Solubility measurements : Saturated solution of the reagent was prepared at room temperature in various solvents and the excess was centrifuged out. Analysis was then done by diluting the aliquot to a convenient concentration.

Distribution constant measurements : A known quantity of *N-p*-chlorophenyl-*p*-methylbenzohydroxamic acid (50 mg) was dissolved in organic solvent (10–25 ml) and shaken vigorously with water (25–100 ml) for 20 min or more at room temperature. The volumes of the two solvents were chosen according to the magnitude of distribution ratio. The two phases were then separated and analysed. The determination of this reagent by its absorbance in the uv region gave unsatisfactory results because of the variation of its characteristics with change in solvent. In the experiments on distribution ratio, where the two immiscible solvents are saturated with each other, the spectral characteristics of the reagent differ from those in pure solvent. Therefore, concentrations were determined spectrophotometrically with vanadium(v)⁷.

For density measurement of the reagent, hydrostatic weighing method was used. All the weighings were corrected for air buoyancy.

NOTE

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